

Study of Clinical, Hematological Profile and Complications of Dengue Fever in an Indian Tertiary Care Hospital: A Cohort Study

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Abstract

Background: In many regions of India, dengue is a serious health concern, and Mangalore is one of its endemic places. A number of variables, including altered hematological and coagulation parameters, have been linked to increased morbidity and death in dengue. Three clinical syndromes, including conventional dengue fever, dengue hemorrhagic fever, and dengue shock syndrome, can result from dengue virus infection. This study's goals included examining the various clinical manifestations of dengue fever as well as its hematological characteristics.

Methods: A total of 130 patients admitted to Father Muller Hospital with a fever greater than 38.5°C and positive IgM tests for dengue were chosen. They were monitored from the time their fever started for twelve days or, if sooner, until they met the WHO's criteria for discharge.

Results: According to WHO criteria, 94 of the 130 patients in this research fall into the DF category, 28 into the DHF category, and 8 into the DSS category. Fever was present in every instance (100%) Myalgia (95.3%), joint pain (76.9%), headache (79.2%), nausea (56.9%), abdominal discomfort (56.9%), rash (45.3%), hepatomegaly (25%), bleeding (21.5%), and shock (6.1%) are other frequent symptoms. In patients with 26.1%, the Hess test was positive. 77% of patients had low platelet counts that met WHO criteria (less than 100,000/cu mm).

Conclusion: Compared to DHF or DSS, dengue fever was a more frequent symptom. Each patient with a fever during an outbreak should have dengue fever seriously examined as a differential diagnosis. Fluid management and supportive care are the major treatments for dengue.

Keywords: Dengue fever, Thrombocytopenia, Dengue hemorrhagic fever, IgM, Dengue, Dengue shock syndrome, WHO.

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Introduction

In terms of morbidity and mortality, dengue is a significant mosquito-borne infection. It has grown to be a significant public health issue in recent years. The arbovirus known as dengue belongs to the family Flaviviridae and is spread by mosquito bites. It is a viral infection carried primarily by *Aedes aegypti*

mosquitoes, but sometimes infrequently by *Aedes albopictus* [1]. Dengue is caused by the DEN-1, DEN-2, DEN- 3, and DEN- 4.2 virus serotypes. The dengue virus causes a variety of ailments, from asymptomatic, self-limiting classical dengue fever (DF) to potentially lethal dengue hemorrhagic fever

(DHF) and dengue shock syndrome (DSS) [2]. Epidemics of dengue have changed from being a random infection to a frequent occurrence all across the world. Dengue fever and dengue hemorrhagic fever are prevalent in parts of Southeast Asia, including Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Burma, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. Dengue is a major cause of hospitalization and fatality in these locations, particularly in children. DF and DHF are prevalent to India. The nation contains all four serotypes. In endemic nations, the case fatality rate is 2.5 percent [3]. Attack rates among vulnerable people during dengue outbreaks range from 40 to 90%. In recent years, dengue incidence and geographic spread have both significantly grown [4]. The goal of the current study was to examine the clinical, hematological, and presenting characteristics of dengue fever.

Methodology

The present study was conducted in Father Muller Medical hospital, Mangalore from the period of May 2010 to April 2012.

Study design

It is a prospective cohort study that uses a sample and sampling methods over a two-year period. Purposive sample procedures

will be used to select 130 hospitalized patients who have a history of a fever of more than 38.5°C and are IgM positive for dengue. They are monitored from the moment of fever start to the moment of recovery or, if sooner, discharge in accordance with WHO discharge standards. Blood counts and IgM dengue tests will both be conducted. Patients are clinically evaluated, and daily platelet and hematocrit measurements are performed.

Inclusion criteria

1. Those admitted in Father Muller hospital having fever more than 38.5 °C.
2. IgM dengue positive.

Exclusion criteria

1. Age less than 15 years or more than 60 years.
2. Preexisting substantial chronic liver, kidney or heart disease.
3. Patients with history of hematological disorders.

Data analysis

Data collected, analyzed by frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation.

Results

Table 1: Clinical spectrum of dengue cases

Diagnosis	Number	Distribution
DF	94	72%
DHF	28	22%
DSS	8	6%
Total	130	100%

Figure 1: Clinical spectrum of Dengue positive cases.

As shown in the clinical spectrum of dengue patients in Table 1 and Figure 1. We looked at a total of 130 individuals who were hospitalized to our hospital with a fever (>101⁰F) and positive IgM test for dengue. Out of 130 individuals, 94 (72%) had DF, 28 (22%) had DHF, and 8 (6%), DSS-based, diagnoses were made for the other patients.

Table 2: Gender wise distribution

Sex	Number	Percentage
Male	80	62%
Female	50	38%
Total	130	100%

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution

The current study comprised 50 (38%) female and 80 (62%) male patients, as indicated in Table 2 and Figure 2. Due to regional dispersion, dengue infection was more common in men.

Table 3: Sex distribution of DF, DHF And DSS

Sex	DF		DHF		DSS	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Female	40	43	8	29	2	25
Male	54	57	20	71	6	75
Total	94	100	28	100	8	100

Figure 3: Sex distribution of DF, DHF AND DSS

According to Table 3 and Figure 3, there were more DF instances among males, 54(57%), than among females, 40(43%). Males made up 20 (71%) more DHF cases than females 8 (29%), totaling 20. Males made up the majority of DSS cases, 6 (75%) against 2 (25%) for females. These data lead us to the conclusion that geographic location affects the occurrence of each clinical spectrum. Because dengue fever is known to be prevalent in the region where our study was done, there was a greater prevalence of the disease there.

Table 4: Age wise distribution

Age	15-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	Total
Frequency(n)	22	60	30	11	7	130

Figure 4: Age wise distribution

It is evident from Table 4 and Figure 4 that the bulk of dengue infection cases (46% of all cases) are found in people between the ages of 21 and 30. In the younger population, it was more prevalent.

Table 5: Analysis of various symptoms and signs

	Present		Absent	
	No. of patients	Percent	No. of patients	Percent
Fever	130	100	0	0
Myalgia	124	95.3	6	4.6
Joint pain	100	76.9	30	23.0
Vomiting	77	59.2	53	40.7
Pain ABD	74	56.9	56	43.0
Rash	59	45.3	71	54.6
Bleeding	28	21.5	102	78.4
Headache	103	79.2	27	20.7
Hepatomegaly	33	25	97	75
Shock	8	6.1	122	93.8

Figure 5: Analysis of various symptoms and signs

Analysis of numerous indications and symptoms in the research population is shown in Table 5 and Figure 5. Fever was found in 130 patients (100%) and myalgia in 124 instances (95.3%). Similar symptoms included headache in 103 cases (79.2%), joint pain in 100 instances (76.9%), vomiting in 77 cases (56.9%), abdominal discomfort in 74 cases (56.9%), rash in 59 cases (45.3%), hepatomegaly in 33 cases (25%) and shock in 8 cases (6.1%).

Table 6: HESS test

	Present		Absent	
	No. of patients	Percent	No. of patients	Percent
HESS	34	26.1	96	73.8

Figure 6: HESS test

The association of the Hess test was explored, as seen in Table 6 and Figure 6. It reveals that 34 (26.1%) of the patients' Hess tests were positive.

Table 7: Platelet count

Platelet	Frequency	Percentage
<100,000	100	77
>100,000	30	23
Total	130	100

Figure 7: Platelet count

As demonstrated in Table 7 and Figure 7, 100 individuals (or 77%) met the WHO criteria for low platelet counts.

Table 8: Total leukocyte count

TLC	Number	Percent
< 4000	66	51%
> 11000	5	3%
4000 - 11000	59	46%
Total	130	100.0%

Figure 8: Total leukocyte count

Out of 130 patients, 59 (46%), as indicated in Table 8 and Figure 8, had total leukocyte counts between 4,000 and 11,000, according to the data. 66 (51%) individuals had a total leukocyte count that was less than 4,000. Five (3%) of the patients had a total leukocyte count over 11,000.

Table 9: Hematocrit

Haematocrit	Number	Percent
Below 40	68	52.3
40 - 45	37	28.4
Above 45	25	19.2
Total	130	100.0

Figure 9: Hematocrit

The hematocrit value ranged from 20.65-60.65% with a mean value of 39.8%, Table 9 and Figure 9. Below 40 Hematocrit value having maximum percentage 52.3% as compared to others.

Table 10: Bradycardia

Bradycardia	Number	Percentage
Present	60	46.15%
Absent	70	53.8%

Figure 10: Bradycardia

Shown in Table 10 and Figure 10, among 130(100%) patients, 60(46.1%) patients had bradycardia.

Table 11: Features of plasma leakage

Evidence of plasma leakage	Percentage	Number
Pedal Edema	9.2%	12
Ascites	15.3%	20
Pleural effusion	20.7%	27
Shock	6.15%	8

Figure 11: Evidence of fluid leakage

In the research, evidence of plasma leakage was seen in the form of pedal edema in 12 (9.2%) patients, pleural effusion in 27 (20.7%) patients, ascites in 20 (15.3%) patients, and shock in 8 (6.15%) patients, as shown in Table 11 and Figure 11.

Discussion

In the current study, there were 50 (38%) female and 80 (62%) male patients, with DF identified in 40 (31%) female and 54 (42%) male patients. The ratio of men to women was 1.6:1, which was consistent with the previous research [5, 6].

In this study, males had a higher prevalence of DSS and DHF than females. 20 (15%) men and 8 (6% of females) were identified as having DHF. 6(7%) men and 2(6%) females had DSS diagnoses.

79% of the study population had dengue fever, according to the current study. DHF and DSS incidence rates were 17% and 4%, respectively [5]. There was a significant prevalence of DHF in another investigation [7].

We may infer from these results that geographic location affects the occurrence of each clinical spectrum. Because dengue fever is known to be prevalent in the region where our study was done, there was a greater prevalence of the disease there.

In every patient in our analysis, fever was the initial complaint. Fever also appeared in the comparison research [8].

Joint aches and myalgia were present in 95.3% and 76.9% of patients, respectively. In a different research, myalgia and joint symptoms were mentioned [5, 6].

In our study, headache was noticed in 79.2% of participants. Identical incidence was also found in other investigations. In the other study, headaches were reported by 85%, 74%, and 75% of participants, respectively. Rash was one of the first symptoms that 45.3% of patients reported. Rash was discovered to be present in 56%, 41%, and 37.8% of the research participants,

respectively. In the comparative study that was done, bleeding was a presenting symptom in 7% of patients, while in our study, the percentage of bleeding was greater, at 22%. In 59.2% and 56.9% of patients, respectively, vomiting and abdominal discomfort were discovered. Some studies failed to note the prevalence of this [9-11].

100 participants (or 77%) in the current study experienced thrombocytopenia. Studies that revealed the prevalence of thrombocytopenia [12, 13] demonstrated a substantial ($p < 0.001$) correlation between thrombocytopenia and dengue virus infection.

In the current investigation, 8 (6.1%) individuals had shock-related symptoms. Another study that was done revealed that 35% of people experience shock. These data lead us to the conclusion that geographic location affects the occurrence of each clinical spectrum [14].

Tourniquet test results and platelet count did not always correlate. In 33 instances, the tourniquet test was positive (26.1%). Divergent outcomes from this exam have been found in other research. As proven by several other Indian research, the tourniquet test is not a valid diagnostic tool [15, 16].

In the current research, 25% of patients had hepatomegaly. Another investigation revealed a greater prevalence of hepatomegaly in patients [17, 1].

The platelet count and the presence of bleeding were compared in the current investigation. Patients with thrombocytopenia experienced bleeding symptoms more frequently than those with a normal platelet count. Hematocrit values varied between 32 and 60%. In the current

study, the mean hematocrit value for dengue positive patients was 39.8%. Hematocrit levels increased in both DHF and DSS. This was consistent with WHO recommendations [18].

Out of 130 patients in the research, 20 (15.3%) patients had ascites, 12 (9.2%) patients had pedal edema, and 27 (20.7%) patients had right sided pleural effusion [5].

Conclusion

Examining the hematological profile and clinical signs of dengue fever was the aim of the current investigation. The presence of dengue fever cannot be ruled out by a negative test, but a positive Hess test should result in close observation and an emergency medical referral. Bleeding tendencies should be closely monitored. When pleural effusion, ascites, or pedal edema are present as indicators of plasma leakage, the patient has to be carefully examined and treated right soon. Most treatments for dengue focus on providing supportive care. Yet, good hydration control significantly affects how the condition progresses.

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